

EXAMINATION OF THE RELATIONSHIPS AMONG ORGANIZATIONAL TRAINING AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

Hassan R. H. Elkhdrⁱ

Lecturer, The High Institute
for Engineering Professions,
Almajurie, Benghazi,
Libya

Abstract:

There is a clear relationship between organizational training and organizational commitment. The relationships between organizational training and organizational commitment has been the main concern of researchers in organizational behavior over the times. This study examined the causal relationship among organizational training and organizational commitment by reviewing previous theoretical and empirical studies on organizational training and organizational commitment. It is also describe the important theoretical approaches. Used data from previous studies to assess the effect of organizational training on organizational commitment. The main findings of this study are that: there is a significant positive association among organizational training and organizational commitment. In addition, the study concludes that the more training giving to employees, the higher their level commitment to the organisation.

Keywords: organizational training, organizational commitment

1. Introduction

Organizational training is an important issue in all organizations. Studies on organizational training seem to confirm that organizational training is one of the most important investments because it enhances the knowledge, updates the appropriate skills, attitudes and behavior of employees, and hence creates an inimitable core competency vital for the organization's competitive sustainability (Mozael,2015; Franco, Bennett, & Kanfer, 2002). In addition to that, investment in organizational training brings many advantages to organizations because organizational training enhances organizational performance. It does this through increasing the skills, motivation and knowledge of employees. Thus, the intellectual capital of organizations is increased (Barney, 2001). The organizational training within organizations creates a resource that

ⁱ Correspondence: email hass_elkader@yahoo.com

is more valuable than any other resource, that is, committed employees, organizational training and organizational commitment are significantly associated with each other (Jex & Britt, 2008).

The literatures of organizational training have emphasized the benefits organizational gained from adopting a systematic approach to organizational training. The development of skills underpins organizational business objectives. According to Brum (2010) and development training will increase organizational commitment, which can further counter the numerous costs associated with employees' turnover. On the other hand, when commitment is low, absenteeism and turnover will be high. Meyer & Allen (1993) says that, organizational training is one of the best strategies that can be used to develop commitment because it facilitates the process of affiliation with the organization as well as making organizational support to the worker concrete.

This paper aims to enhance the understanding of the effect and the relationship between organizational training and organizational commitment within workplace. The structure of this paper is; first section an introduction, the second section present a review about organizational training, in the third section organizational commitment has been discussed, and the last section about the relationship between organizational training and organizational commitment, then the final will draw some conclusions.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Organizational Training

Several researches have examined the relationship between organizational training and organizational commitment. Recent years organizational training has become a major factor where it differentiates the organizations are successful or not. Good organizational training practices can lead to high organizational commitment and different studies justify them. Many studies show that organizational commitment can plays a very important role in the increased efficiency of employees and organization (Marchington & Wilkinson, 2005). Organizations can achieve its goals through the organizational training practices and the importance of ensuring employees' commitment and retention following organizational training may lie in the strategic approach that is utilized. In an attempt to ensure that the employee remains with the organization following organizational training, employers may implement a strategy to organizational training that fosters commitment (Brum, 2010).

Organizational training helps organizations to improve quality and to give their employees a vision of what the organization needs to become and the skills and knowledge they need to have made that transition. It also helps an organization to compete successfully. If organizations are to compete successfully, one crucial part of their activities must be that meet the future training requirements of the organization. Organizational training makes an individual or group of people more efficient and effective (Scott, Clothier & Spriegel, 1977).

Organizational training is at the heart of modern management practice in any organization (Purcell, 2000). Organizational training refers to systematic activities to develop and improve employees' skills, knowledge and behaviors to enable them to perform job-related duties, accomplish specific tasks and meet the quality requirements of human resource for the future (Ahmad & Bakar, 2003).

2.2 Definitions of Organizational Training

Barry, (1994) defines training as: "*a process by which people are taught skills and given the necessary knowledge or attitude to enable them to carry out their responsibilities to the required standard*". Manpor Services Commission (MSC) (1981) cited in (Armstrong, 1999) defines training as: "*a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge or skill behavior through learning experience to achieve performance in an activity or range of activities its purpose, in work situation is to develop the abilities of the individual and to satisfy the current and future needs of the organization*". Department of Employments Glossary of Training Term (1981) defines training as "*the systematic development of the attitude, knowledge, skill, behavior, and pattern required by an individual to perform adequately a given task or job.*"

This definition is similar in principal to other definitions given by writers on the subject (Armstrong, 1999). From these definitions, some basic characteristics about training can be observed. Firstly, training is a formal and conscious activity designed to achieve the stated objectives. Secondly, there is a learning process embedded in training. This learning process endeavors to develop and modify knowledge, skills performance, and attitudes. In a more specific way, Department of Employments Glossary of Training Term (1981) contends that training attempts to modify and direct one's abilities toward a particular activity. Finally, within organizations, the investment in training is intended to result in improved performance of both the learners and the organization.

2.3 Benefits of Organizational Training

Organizational training is most probably the best strategy known to the corporate world to develop employees' skills and behaviors. Nordhaug (1989) pointed out three types of employee benefits, which they receive when they participate in training programs. They experience higher learning motivation, more career progress and better psychosocial situation. Both Noe and Wilk (1993) categorized benefits of employee participation in three categories: personal, job-related, and career related. Personal benefits can be political, social, or psychological. Job-related advantages may be pertaining to improvement in the overall performance in the coming times. Career-related advantages help identifying the overall career objectives and generate more opportunities.

2.4 Importance of Organizational Training

Organizational training is a significant area, on which, the whole structure of HR development and management focuses because it directly affects the effectiveness of

workforce and besides, it helps optimum use of work force. These days, very few experts disagree with the idea of corporate or labor organizational training because it is vital area for any organization's success. Companies invest in organizational training for value addition in this very expensive resource (Huselid, 1995).

During downsizing, creating structural flexibility and devolution of power to the workforce helps creating an environment of coaching and support. Another important need for organizational training is induction training, which almost every organization provides to the newly inducted staff. It assures technical and social competence of the staff that makes its headway towards the organization's leadership roles. All this shows that organizational training is a continuous need of the any organization that is willing to improve the expertise and behavior of its staff; therefore, organizational training is an integral part of the total quality management (Elnaga and Imran, 2013).

Cole (2002) has written in his famous book "Personnel and Human Resource Management" that training or organizational learning activities must be directed towards specific knowledge/skills for making the staff skilled for of an occupation or a task. Trainers should focus on improving people's performance and safety during the operations requiring the use of plants or machines. Every organization should provide organizational training to its sales team for assuring its survival in the market. For bringing the employees to the desired level of expertise and behavior, organizational training must increase employee commitment and motivation (Cole, 2002; Meyer and Smith, 2000). finally, the main aim of organizational training is to give individuals the knowledge and skills they need to perform effectively in their fields of expertise (Kum, Cowden & Karodia, 2014).

2.5 Training Methods

Generally, trainings can be either on-the-job or off the job; however, on-the-job training approach is more popular because it is conducted under the supervision of a manager, consultant, experienced worker, supervisor, or trainer. This type of training not only helps developing skills but relationships as well because it provides senior workers with a chance to mentor and develop juniors and newcomers, which improves mutual cooperation, confidence, respect and loyalty. On-the-job training can be beneficial or problematic because an employee confronts with issues and learns at the same time, so it might compromise learning. It also accrues certain costs. On one hand, experts believe that the expenses made during on-the-job training are investments but on the other, investors believe that they are part of cost structure because sometimes, management sends people out of the work environment and hire sophisticated trainers (Gomez-Mejia, Balkin, & Cardy, 2012).

Off-the-job training is alternative to on-the-job training. In this type of training, an institution or center provides training to trainees through recognized vocational courses. Formal courses, diplomas, vocational and scientific trainings are included in this type of training. Off-the-job training is beneficial in the sense that employees get training for longer periods, and besides, getting training in a classroom can make the

educational process easier and formal without interruptions, which typically take place in the of-the-job training environment. A major disadvantage of the off-the-job training may be that the learned skill might not transfer back to the job mainly because a classroom is quite different as compared to a workplace. Some employees think that off-the-job training is an enjoyment opportunity, so, their learning remains compromised (Gomez-Mejia et al., 2012).

2.6 Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment has been a topic of extensive interest in the organizational behavior literature since the 1950's. It has been associated with employees with high levels of organizational commitment, including decreased turnover, decreased absenteeism, increased job performance, and decreased stress. Organizational commitment at its most basic level is similar to loyalty, and it is related to one's intent to stay in one's current position. Organizational commitment is also related to job satisfaction, but it is distinct and is much less transient. (Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch & Topolnytsky, L. 2002).

There are several definitions for organizational commitment. Simply, it can be defined as "*a psychological state that binds the individual to the organization (i.e. makes turnover and absenteeism less likely)*" (Allen & Meyer, 1990). Liao, Hu & Chung (2009) have defined Organizational commitment as "*the strong desire to be continued to be a member of an organization. It plays a positive role in retention of members in the organization*". Mowday et al. (1979) also states that organizational commitment as individuals believing in and accepting organizational goals and values, willing to remain within their organizations, and willing to provide considerable effort on their behalf (Liao et al., 2009).

According to Porter, Steers & Porter (1976) organizational commitment could be defined as the feelings and beliefs formed internally or as a set of intentions that enriches and employee's desire to remain with an organization and to accept its major goals and values. Organizational commitment has also been described as a mindset that influences the behavior of an individual and binds the individual to a particular course of action. It characterizes the employee's relationship with the organization and has implications for the decision to continue or discontinue membership in the organization. Depending on how it develops, commitment to the organization may take forms such as affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

Mowday, Porter, & Steers (1982) also identified three characteristics of organizational commitment: (a) a strong belief in and acceptance of the organization's goals and values; (b) willingness to exert considerable effort on behalf of the organization; and (c) a strong desire to maintain membership in the organization (Joo, Yin, Xu, Thia, Chia, Kuah & He, 2010). The extensive literature on commitment has explored different types or bases of commitment to an organization, Meyer, Allen & Smith. (1993) proposed a three-component model of organizational commitment; it was

created to argue that commitment has three different components that correspond with different psychological states. Meyer and Allen's research indicated that there are three "mind sets" which can characterize an employee's commitment to the organization.

Organizational commitment is a type of ties that bind employees with a desire to remain and continue attached to their organization. If employees are committed to towards about their organization they will perform their job very well and will be the ultimate performance of the organization to be better, also increase organizational commitment to employees by committing people values primarily through the provision of appropriate organizational training and benefits, and so also through communication and clarify the message the organization's vision and goals, employee development support and security etc. (Luthans, 2002).

3. Discussion

Recent studies have shown that organizational training is the most important and vital factor of economic development. Better education, improved skills, and provision of healthy atmosphere will result in proper and most efficient use of resources, resulting in economic growth. Nowadays, the success of any organization is depending on skills, knowledge, experience, and the commitment of its employees, employees needs to be skillful and professionally strong in order to survive. Only satisfied, committed and motivated employees are meeting the level of expectations, expanding their skill horizon, through training which holds the key to success. Organizational training has several benefits like provide abilities knowledge and skills that enhance individual performance and it ultimately lead towards firm's performance and productivity, employees' job satisfaction and commitment and decrease the level of turnover (Thang, 2009). If we look into the organizational behavior literature available, there are many studies addressing specifically the relationship between organizational training and organizational commitment in different sectors different places around the world. These researches following:

Paul & Anantharaman, (2004) have made a research on Influence of human resource management practices on organizational commitment among software professionals in India which revealed that training programmes show a significant positive relationship with organizational commitment. The research conducted by Herrbach (2009) designed the relations among perceived training, organizational commitment, and voluntary early retirement in France and found that training is most favorable factor which enhances the higher effective and high sacrifice commitment and reduced voluntary early retirement.

Amir, Rana & Asma, (2013) has shown that there is significant positive relationship between training and organizational commitment among banking sector of two major cities of Pakistan. Shah, Hussain & Rahman (2016) also, found out that training have a positive effect on organizational commitment among the employees working in private healthcare sector. Furthermore, results revealed that the employees

who are participating in training programs, they are likely to be more committed with their employers than those who perceive training a leisure activity.

Bulut, & Culha (2010) in their empirical study among hotels sector investigated the impact of training on organizational commitment, furthermore, argues that all training positively affected organizational commitment. Another researcher, Alba & Antonio (2012) also, presents a study in Information Technology Company in Brazil; it was found that affective commitment has a strong and positive relationship with training.

As mentioned above, that organizational commitment has multi-level of effect, individual's level contributes to raising job satisfaction which is reflected in lower turnover, absenteeism and a sense of job security they have, either at the organization's level, it increases the level of belonging to the organization, productivity and reduce the cost resulting for absent workers and non-performance jobs efficiently and effectively. The important question arises that, how organizational training can play a role to be a main source of firm's productivity, employees' job satisfaction and decrease turnover and absenteeism? This perspective is analyzed through the terms of organizational commitment. In other words, any organization concerned to provide organizational training to its employees gives a good impression of care and attention. It shows that organization invests in human resource and they acknowledge their significance in term of overall organizational performance. This organization is very attractive to the employees because of emotional attachment to give something in return. They will be loyal with the organization and more interested to stay in this organization that offer organizational training because it increases the employability (Groot & Brink, 2000).

4. Conclusion

The aims this study were to enhance the understanding of the impact of organizational training on organizational commitment based on reviewing previous theoretical and empirical studies, it is shown that there is a positive impact and relationship between organizational training and organizational commitment. In accordance with the literature, the conclusion of this study shows that organizational training has significant effect on organizational commitment and are associated with superior organizational performance. Result comes from different sectors as, banking, IT, and hotels and different places as, India, France, Pakistan, Turkey, and Brazil. However, whenever employees are trained, they are more motivated, committed and satisfied. Also, when employees are more committed, they tend to be more skilled, knowledgeable, dedicated and well experienced. This directs to an overall organization culture where employees are focused, thoughtful, considerate and selfless working as one unit to achieve organizational goals. Therefore, it is proved in this study that, organizational training has significant effect on organizational commitment and which is further related to retention of knowledgeable and skilled employees.

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